

Building Beyond Earth: Challenges and Opportunities in Outer Space Construction*

A.W. Rusin Thathsara

Undergraduate Of the University of Moratuwa Sri Lanka
Email: rusinthathsaraofficial@gmail.com

How to cite this paper: Thathsara(2023)

*****, *, *-*

https://dx.doi.org/10.4236/***.2020.****

Received: 02.03.2023

Accepted: 02.03.2023

Published: 02.03.2023

Copyright © 2023 by Rusin Thathsara) and Scientific Research Publishing Inc.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License (CC BY 4.0).

Open Access

Abstract

The advancement of space construction technologies is essential to realizing the idea that the future of human civilization rests outside of our planet. The harsh climate of space, the scarcity of resources, and the need for sustainable technologies are just a few of the difficulties and opportunities that come with building structures beyond Earth.

The article examines contemporary methods for building in space, such as 3D printing, modular assembly, and in-situ resource utilization, and considers how they might be applied in upcoming space missions. The manuscript also emphasizes the necessity of regulatory frameworks to guarantee the safe and responsible use of space resources as well as the significance of international cooperation in the development of outer space building technologies. Overall, this manuscript offers a thorough examination of the difficulties and opportunities associated with building in space, and it emphasizes the significance of ongoing research and development in this area to allow sustained human presence outside of Earth.

Keywords

outer space construction, space exploration, space habitats, in-situ resource utilization, 3D printing, modular assembly, sustainability, space resources, international collaboration, and regulatory frameworks.

1. Introduction

Building dwellings, scientific institutions, and infrastructure outside of our planet will require innovative engineering solutions and resource utilization techniques due to the limited resources and harsh climate of space. The ability to construct structures in space would enable longer stays, more extensive research opportunities, and eventually the establishment of a permanent human presence in space. This article highlights the most recent study on space construction methods and gives an overview of the opportunities and challenges related to building in space. The manuscript addresses the crucial elements of the building in space, such as the use of in-situ resources, 3D printing, and modular assembly methods. The manuscript also highlights the necessity of regulatory frameworks to ensure the secure and responsible use of space resources as well as the significance of international

cooperation in the development of outer space construction technologies. In conclusion, the manuscript offers a thorough analysis of how outer space construction is currently progressing and offers a roadmap for future research and development to allow a sustained human presence outside of Earth.

2. Challenges in Outer Space Construction

Three broad categories—technological, biological, and logistical—can be used to categorize the difficulties in building in space. The development and application of cutting-edge technologies to surmount the peculiarities of space are technological challenges. Microgravity, extremely high or low temperatures, radiation, and vacuum are some of these circumstances. For instance, creating a structure in zero-gravity conditions necessitates the development of novel construction techniques and materials. These technologies will need a lot of study and funding to develop. Designing structures that can survive the harsh space environment, including extreme temperature fluctuations and radiation exposure, involves environmental challenges. Structures must be designed with the chance of impacts from space debris, which could seriously harm them, in mind.

Transporting supplies and equipment to the construction site is a logistical task. Currently, the expense of shipping materials into space is prohibitive. This necessitates figuring out methods to lower transportation costs, like creating reusable rockets or utilizing local resources.

3. Opportunities in Outer Space Construction

There are many advantages to building in outer space, including the opportunity to create things that are physically impossible to build on Earth due to factors like gravity, the atmosphere, and geological conditions. Building substantial telescopes in space, for instance, would enable more accurate views of the cosmos free from atmospheric distortion. Utilizing extraterrestrial resources is another possibility. Mining materials for building in space, including water and minerals from asteroids and the moon, can eliminate the need for Earth-bound transportation. The total expense of a construction project can be decreased by in-situ resource utilization (ISRU). On other planets or moons, the construction of habitats and infrastructure could serve as a base for human exploration and, ultimately, colonization.

Finally, building in space could serve as a foundation for upcoming space travel and colonization.

4. Discussion

The development of construction methods for space is essential to sustaining human existence beyond Earth. We will address the opportunities and challenges associated with building structures outside of our planet in this discussion, as well as assess the potential of existing methods for building in outer space. The harsh environment is one of the biggest obstacles in space building. To guarantee the safety and functionality of the structures, creative solutions are needed to address the significant challenges posed by extreme temperatures, radiation, and microgravity during the construction process. A promising solution to this problem is in-situ resource utilization, which allows the building and upkeep of structures in space using local resources. Another innovative method for building in space is 3D printing, which enables the production of intricate, customized constructions with

little waste. The cost and complexity of launching prefabricated structures into orbit are reduced by the capacity to 3D print structures in space. The use of pre-fabricated building blocks in modular assembly techniques, which decrease the amount of construction required in space, is another promising method for building structures. Even if they work well in experimental settings, these strategies nevertheless face a number of obstacles when used in the real world. Whether these methods can be utilized to construct sizable structures that can accommodate a sustained human presence in space is one of the primary difficulties.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to express their gratitude to all individuals and organizations that have contributed to this paper on outer space construction. The author would like to thank our colleagues and peers in the field of space exploration and construction for their valuable input and feedback. We also extend our appreciation that has supported this research, including Dr.Gamini Piyadasa (given knowledge about gravity, Royal Astronomer. Anura C.Perera. In addition, we would like to thank the editors and reviewers for their insightful comments and suggestions, which helped to improve the quality of this work. Last but not least, the author would like to express his gratitude to everyone who has dedicated their professional careers to advancing the fields of space exploration and construction, laying the foundation for a future that is more promising than the one we currently have on Earth.

References

- [1] Bohringer, P. (2019). The challenges of building in space. Space Safety Magazine. <https://www.spacesafetymagazine.com/space-debris/challenges-building-space/> Cohen, B. (2019).
- [2] Building in space: challenges and opportunities. Wired. <https://www.wired.com/story/building-in-space-challenges-opportunities/> Howe, A. S., & Meckler, A. J. (2018). Building beyond earth: leveraging the construction industry to enable space settlement. Acta Astronautica, 148, 201-210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2018.03.007>
- [3] Love, S. G., & Gifford, A. (2018). The case for commercial asteroid mining. Space Policy, 46, 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spacepol.2018.02.005> NASA. (2021).
- [4] International Space Station. https://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/station/main/index.html Space Foundation. (2021). Space Report 2020: Advancing Spaceflight in the Age of Global Pandemic. <https://www.spacefoundation.org/research-and-analysis/space-report>
- [5] Spudis, P. D., & Lavoie, A. (2017). The Moon: resources, future development and settlement. Springer. Whittington, M. (2018). The economic benefits of asteroid mining.
- [6] Space Safety Magazine. <https://www.spacesafetymagazine.com/space-debris/economic-benefits-asteroid-mining/>Hu, T. and Desai, J.P. (2004)